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Abstract: Vine shoots were hydrothermally processed and the effect of the different assayed severities on the subsequent enzymatic saccharification of the remaining solids was evaluated. The solid obtained at a severity of 4.47 showed the highest yield on glucose (74.01%) and therefore, it was used as the substrate for the obtaining of bio-ethanol through a SSF process. Under the evaluated conditions (LSR 10 g/g, 20 FPU/g and 10 IU/FPU) 13.3 g/L of bio-ethanol were produced (corresponding to 67.4% of ethanol conversion). Moreover, lignin has been extracted by an alkali delignification treatment from the vine shoots unprocessing and from the solids resulting from the stages of the proposed biorefinery scheme, which were the autohydrolysed vine shoots and the bio-ethanol residue. The isolated lignins were characterized by HPLC, total phenolic content, FTIR, HPSEC, Py-GC/MS and TGA and it was observed that the successive stages of processing to which the vine shoots were submitted provoked chemical and structural changes in the extracted lignins. The knowledge of the structural modifications that the lignin present in the vine shoots during the autohydrolysis and the SSF process could help determining at which stage of the bio-ethanol production would be suitable to recover the lignin for value-added applications.

Keywords: Biorefinery, Bio-ethanol, Lignin, Enzymatic hydrolysis, Structural characterization, Lignocellulosic ethanol residue

Multiproduct biorefinery from vine shoots: Bio-ethanol and lignin production

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Abstract

Vine shoots were hydrothermally processed and the effect of the different assayed severities on the subsequent enzymatic saccharification of the remaining solids was evaluated. The solid obtained at a severity of 4.47 showed the highest yield on glucose (74.01%) and therefore, it was used as the substrate for the obtaining of bio-ethanol through a SSF process. Under the evaluated conditions (LSR 10 g/g, 20 FPU/g and 10 IU/FPU) 13.3 g/L of bio-ethanol were produced (corresponding to 67.4% of ethanol conversion). Moreover, lignin has been extracted by an alkali delignification treatment from the vine shoots unprocessing and from the solids resulting from the stages of the proposed biorefinery scheme, which were the autohydrolysed vine shoots and the bio-ethanol residue. The isolated lignins were characterized by HPLC, total phenolic content, FTIR, HPSEC, Py-GC/MS and TGA and it was observed that the successive stages of processing to which the vine shoots were submitted provoked chemical and structural changes in the extracted lignins. The knowledge of the structural modifications that the lignin present in the vine shoots during the autohydrolysis and the SSF process could help determining at which stage of the bio-ethanol production would be suitable to recover the lignin for value-added applications.

Keywords: Biorefinery, bio-ethanol, lignin, enzymatic hydrolysis, structural characterization, lignocellulosic ethanol residue

1. Introduction

Currently, the problem of the fossil resources depletion is directly related with their treatment under a linear economy concept. Liguori and Faraco [1] speculated that the fossil resources such as oil, coal and gas could disappear in 35, 107 and 37 years time, respectively. In order to replace the petroleum-based fuels the employment of biomass in the production of bio-ethanol, biodiesel or bio-hydrogen has gained great importance in the last decades [2]. Lignocellulosic biomass due to its great availability and limited price [3] is supposed to be one of the most promising raw material for the production of biofuels. Among them, bio-ethanol has been considered as one of the most encouraging bio-fuels, as it is renewable and environmentally clean [4]. The production of bio-fuels from lignocellulosic biomass generally involves a hydrolysis step and a subsequent fermentation for the conversion of sugars into bio-ethanol [5]. Commonly the hydrolysis step consists on an enzymatic saccharification in which the cell wall of the biomass is deconstructed releasing monosaccharides to the media. However, due to the complexity and heterogeneity of the structure of the lignocellulosic biomass a first treatment is necessary to increase the enzymatic digestibility of the substrate. The removal of the hemicellulosic fraction from the raw material could enhance its enzymatic digestibility, as it has been reported that this fraction could act as a physical barrier preventing the approach of the enzyme to the cellulose [6].

Among the different treatments described in the literature, the hydrothermal treatment is considered as one of the most adequate technique for the fractionation of biomass and for the improvement of its susceptibility towards enzymatic saccharification.

Once the three main fractions of the lignocellulosic biomass are separated, each one can be converted in a wide range of bio-based products (food, feed, chemicals) and bioenergy (biofuels, power and heat) that can replace the fossil-based products [1]. This approach would enable an integrated revalorization of the biomass following a biorefinery concept which is the base of the circular economy, accomplishing the reduction, the reuse and the recycling (approach 3Rs) of wastes and the purport to achieve a close-loop system so as to maximize the recovery of feedstocks derived from the residue at end of life [1].

In this context, the integral exploitation of renewable resources to obtain bio-fuels following a biorefinery proposal could contribute to the achievement of a circular economy. Several authors have reported the bio-ethanol production from the liquid and solid phases obtained from the hydrothermal treatment of different raw materials accomplishing their full recycling and re-use. Bioethanol has been produced by simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF) by Vargas et al. [7] and Domínguez et al. [8], obtaining 51.7 g EtOH/L and 52.7 g EtOH/L from autohydrolysed barley straw with a severity (S_0) of 4.21 and autohydrolysed *Paulownia tormentosa* wood ($S_0 = 4.72$), respectively. Egüés et al. [9] employed the liquors obtained in the autohydrolysis of grape stalks to produce 20.84 g EtOH/L by fermentation.

An important issue in the production of bio-ethanol from lignocellulosic materials, is the generation of huge amounts of residues which have been traditionally used as fuel and for power generation in order to drive the fermentation and the distillation steps [10]. However, the utilization of these lignocellulosic ethanol residues (LER), as a bio-resource to develop products derived from its lignin fraction could improve the economic viability of the bioethanol production process [11].

Taking into account the previous ideas, in this study we raise a suitable integrated process for the production of second-generation bio-ethanol from hydrothermally processed vine shoots and for the recovery of lignin from the LER, following a biorefinery approach. In a previous study, it has been demonstrated that the autohydrolysis permitted the efficient removal of the hemicelluloses from vine shoots, eliminating a 92.0% of them and yielding a solid with 33.7% of glucan, 2.5% of hemicelluloses and 55.1% of lignin when the treatment was carried out at $S_0 = 4.65$ [12]. The present research proposes the effective utilization of the remaining components of the hydrothermally treated vine shoots to improve the economic viability of an integrated biorefinery based on vine shoots [13].

In this work, firstly we studied the influence of the severity of the hydrothermal treatment on the enzymatic saccharification of the pretreated solids; then, the solid and liquid phases obtained under the more suitable conditions of hydrothermal treatment for the enzymatic hydrolysis, which were those that permitted the obtaining of the solid with the highest enzymatic digestibility, were converted separately into bio-ethanol. Due to the scarce information about the lignin isolated from the residual solid that remains after the bio-ethanol production, in this study, after the SSF, the lignin was extracted from the LER to carry out a deep characterization. The lignin extraction was performed by an alkali delignification treatment and the lignin was characterized by HPLC, total phenolic content, FTIR, HPSEC, Py-GC/MS and TGA. The chemical and structural characteristics of the lignin isolated from the LER were compared with the ones observed in the lignins extracted from the untreated and hydrothermally treated vine shoots using the same procedure. The biorefinery scheme followed in this work is shown in Fig. 1.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Raw material

The vine shoots employed in this work were supplied by the local winery Aldako Bodega S. L. (Basque Country, Spain). After being air-dried, the vine shoots were milled and sieved in order to have a homogenized lot with a particle size smaller than 0.4 mm. These residues were stored in a dark and dry place until their use. The composition of the vine shoots has been published in a previous work [12].

Fig. 1. Flow chart followed to revalorize the vine shoots under a biorefinery perspective.

2.2. Hydrothermal processing of the vine shoots

The vine shoots were subjected to hydrothermal treatments using a 1.5 L stainless steel Parr reactor [12]. Water and vine shoots were mixed at a liquid to solid ratio of 8 g/g (oven-dried basis). The vine shoots were hydrothermally treated in a non-isothermal regimen working in a range of temperature between 180 and 215 °C ($S_0 = 3.29-4.65$). After cooling the reactor, the solid and liquid phases were separated by filtration, being the liquid phase frozen and the solid phase washed with water and stored at 4 °C until further use. The determination of the composition of these solids was performed following the methodology described by Dávila et al. [12].

The intensity of the hydrothermal treatment was measured by the severity (S_0). This parameter is defined as the logarithm of the severity factor (R_0), and it considers the effect caused by the time and temperature along the non-isothermal treatment, including both the heating and cooling period. The applied equation was the following [7]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_0 &= \log R_0 = \log[R_{0Heating} + R_{0Cooling}] \\
 &= \log \left[\int_0^{t_{Max}} e^{\left(\frac{T(t)-T_{Ref}}{\omega}\right)} dt + \int_{t_{Max}}^{t_F} e^{\left(\frac{T'(t)-T_{Ref}}{\omega}\right)} dt \right] \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

where t_{Max} is the time (in min) needed to achieve the maximum temperature of each hydrothermal treatment (T_{Max} , °C), t_F is the time (in min) required for the entire heating-cooling cycles, $T(t)$ and $T'(t)$ (°C) are the temperature profiles in heating and cooling, respectively. ω and T_{Ref} are parameters whose values have been reported in the literature ($\omega = 14.75$ °C; $T_{Ref} = 100$ °C).

2.3. Enzymatic hydrolysis of the hydrothermally processed vine shoots

The enzymatic hydrolysis of the solids obtained in the hydrothermal treatments carried out at different temperatures was performed at 48.5 °C in Erlenmeyer flasks with an orbital agitation of 150 rpm using a liquid to solid ratio (LSR) of 20 g/g (oven-dried basis). The pH of the suspensions was adjusted to 4.85 using a 0.05 N citric acid-sodium citrate buffer. The commercial preparation of *Trichoderma reesei* cellulases “Celluclast 1.5” and a β -glucosidase “Novozyme 188” supplied by Novozyme (Madrid, Spain) were used under a β -glucosidase to cellulase ratio (Cb/Cl) of 10 IU/FPU. The enzyme (cellulases) to solid ratio (ESR) was fixed at 20 FPU/g (oven-dried basis). Additionally, based on the results obtained in these experiments, the enzymatic hydrolysis of the solid obtained in the hydrothermal treatment that allowed to achieve the higher glucose yield was also carried out using a LSR of 10 g/g (oven-dried basis). The decrease of the LSR allows the achievement of a higher glucose concentration and therefore, a greater bio-ethanol production in the subsequent SSF experiments.

2.3.1. Characterization of the liquors obtained in the enzymatic hydrolysis

2.3.1.1. Monosaccharide analysis

At given reaction times, samples were withdrawn from the reaction media of the enzymatic hydrolysis, centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min, diluted and filtered through 0.2 mm of cellulose acetate membranes. These samples were subjected to HPLC analysis for the quantification of monosaccharides (glucose, xylose and arabinose) following the method reported earlier [12].

2.3.1.2. Acid soluble lignin (ASL) determination

The percentage of acid soluble lignin solubilized during the enzymatic hydrolysis was determined by analyzing the liquid phases from the enzymatic hydrolysis obtained after 96 h using an UVmini-1240 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu Corporation). The samples were diluted with H_2SO_4 1M until the absorption at 205 nm was between 0.1 and 0.8 (TAPPI UM250 μ m-83). The acid soluble lignin was quantified by the following equation:

$$\%ASL = \frac{Abs_{205nm} * DF * VF}{\epsilon * D} * 100 \quad (2)$$

where Abs_{250nm} is the absorption (relative to 1M H₂SO₄ at 205 nm), DF is the dilution factor, VF is the volume filtrate, ϵ is the extinction coefficient of the lignin (110 L x cm/g) and DM_i is the weight of the sample used in the enzymatic hydrolysis (g as 100% dry matter).

2.3.1.3. Total phenolic content (TPC) analysis.

The liquid phases from the enzymatic hydrolysis obtained after 96 h were subjected to the evaluation of their total phenolic content. The TPC was determined according to the Folin-Ciocalteu spectrophotometric method [14] and it was expressed as g of gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/L enzymatic liquors.

2.3.2. Characterization of the remaining solids from the enzymatic hydrolysis

The solid phases obtained after 96 h of enzymatic hydrolysis were separated by filtration, washed with water and air-dried. Then, they were subjected to gravimetric and moisture determinations to calculate the solid yield and the amount of solubilized substrate. The composition of the solids was analyzed using the analytical methods described by Dávila et al. [12].

2.4. Production of bio-ethanol from the liquid and solid phases obtained from the hydrothermal processing of the vine shoots

2.4.1. Microorganism and inoculum preparation

Saccharomyces cerevisiae (Ethanol Red® Dry Yeast, Fermentas, France) was employed for simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF) of the cellulose-rich solid obtained after autohydrolysis treatment. *Scheffersomyces stipitis* strain CECT 1922 was used to ferment the xylose hydrolysates obtained under the more suitable conditions for the enzymatic hydrolysis. Cells were grown at 32 °C for 24 h in a 100mL Erlenmeyer flask with orbital agitation (150 rpm) in a media that contained 10 g/L of glucose, 5 g/L of peptone, 3 g/L of malt extract and 3 g/L of yeast extract.

2.4.2. Simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF) of processed vine shoots

The hydrothermally processed vine shoots which presented the highest enzymatic digestibility were used as substrate for the production of second generation bio-ethanol following the SSF approach. The SSF media was prepared as follows: the processed vine shoots and water were mixed and autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min separately from the nutrients. Once the media was cooled down the SSF experiments were started by adding the nutrients (the same concentrations used for the yeast growth media), the enzymes and the yeast inoculum (with an initial cell concentration of 1.2 g/L). The selected operational conditions for the SSF were a LSR 10 g/g, an ESR 20 FPU/g and a β -glucosidase to cellulase ratio (Cb/Ci) of 10 IU/FPU. The SSF trials were

performed in 100mL Erlenmeyer flasks (working volume, 50 mL) using an orbital shaker at 35 °C, 120 rpm and at a pH = 5 during 48 h.

Samples were taken from the media at given fermentation times and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min. Aliquots of the supernatants were withdrawn, diluted, filtered through 0.2 µm cellulose acetate membranes and assayed by HPLC for monosaccharides, ethanol and acetic acid quantification. SSF trials were performed in duplicate.

2.4.3. Fermentation of posthydrolysed liquors of vine shoots

Autohydrolysis liquors obtained under the same conditions that the solid used for the SSF process were subjected to an acid posthydrolysis with 0.5% H₂SO₄ at 125 °C for 165 min to cleave the oligosaccharides into the corresponding sugars. The liquid phase obtained in the posthydrolysis was neutralized with CaCO₃ to a final pH of 6.5 and the CaSO₄ that precipitated was separated from the supernatant by filtration. The neutralized posthydrolysed liquors were detoxified by contacting sequentially with two exchange ionic resins, firstly with a cationic and then with an anionic resins, using a liquor to resin ratio of 15 g/g and 30 min of stirring. The liquors were concentrated under vacuum, recovered by filtration and analyzed by HPLC. These liquors were used as carbon source for the bio-ethanol production.

The posthydrolysed and detoxified liquors were supplemented with the nutrients described in Section 2.4.1. except glucose and the fermentation was started with the addition of the inoculum from *Scheffersomyces stipitis* (5% v/v with an initial cell concentration of 1.3 g/L). The experiments were carried out in 100 mL Erlenmeyers flasks (50 mL) at 35 °C 120 rpm during 96 h. At given fermentation times, samples were withdrawn from the media and processed as indicated in section 2.4.2. The fermentation experiments were performed in duplicate.

2.5. Characterization of the remaining solid from the SSF

The SSF media was filtered and the solid phase was washed several times with water to remove the residual nutrients and the metabolites generated along the experiment. The spent solid from the SSF experiment was stored at 4 °C for further processing. Moreover, an aliquot of this solid was air-dried to determinate its composition following the methodology described by Dávila et al. [12].

2.6. Lignin extraction from the remaining solid from the SSF

The lignin from the spent solid obtained after the SSF was extracted in wet with NaOH at 12% (w/w) using a LSR of 10 g/g at 124 °C for 105 min [15]. After the delignification treatment the solid phase and the liquid phase (black liquor) were separated by filtration. The solid phase was washed with a solution of 12% (w/w) NaOH several times and then with water until it was neutralized. Then it was air-dried and subjected to gravimetric and moisture determinations to

calculate the solid yield and the amount of solubilized substrate. The determination of the composition of the dried solid was carried out following the procedure described by Dávila et al. [12].

On the other hand, the solubilized lignin present in the black liquors was precipitated by acidifying the solution with H₂SO₄ at 96% (w/w) up to pH 2 in an ice bath. The precipitated lignin was recovered by filtration, washed with acidified water and then neutralized with water. The isolated lignin was air-dried and stored for further characterization. In order to compare the chemical and structural characteristics of this lignin, the untreated and the hydrothermally treated vine shoots with the highest enzymatic digestibility were also subjected to an alkali delignification treatment under the same conditions used for the solid obtained in the SSF.

2.7. Extracted lignins characterization

2.7.1. Chemical characterization

The composition of the isolated lignins in saccharides, acid soluble lignin (ASL) and Klason lignin was determined by a modification of the procedure carried out by Erdocia et al. [16]. The lignins were subjected to an acid hydrolysis with 72% (w/w) H₂SO₄ for 1 h at 30 °C followed by a second acid hydrolysis carried out by diluting the samples to 12% (w/w) H₂SO₄ and autoclaving them for 1 h at 121 °C. After the hydrolysis the samples were filtered and the remaining solid phase was considered as Klason lignin. The liquid phases were analyzed by HPLC for the determination of monosaccharides, galacturonic acid, acetic acid and degradation products (hydroxymethylfurfural and furfural). The ASL was determined following the method described in section 2.3.1.2.

The ash content of the isolated lignins was determined by a TGA/SDTA RSI analyzer 851 Mettler Toledo. Between 3 and 5 mg of the lignin were analyzed using an air atmosphere and working with a heating rate of 10 °C/min from 25 °C to 1000 °C [17].

2.7.2. Determination of total phenolic content

The total phenolic content of the lignin samples was determined following the procedure reported by Morales et al. (2018) [18]. Briefly, 0.3 mL of each lignin solution (0.24 g/L in DMSO) was mixed with 2.5 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 2 mL of Na₂CO₃ 7.5% (w/v). The preparations were kept in a thermostatic bath at 50 °C for 5 min, and afterwards the absorbance of the samples was registered at 760 nm. The percentage of the total phenolic content of the lignins was expressed as % of gallic acid equivalent.

2.7.3. Structural characterization

2.7.3.1. High performance size exclusion chromatography (HPSEC)

The average molecular weight (M_w), the number-average (M_n) and the polydispersity index (M_w/M_n) of the isolated lignins were analyzed by HPSEC using a Jasco LC Net II/ADC chromatograph equipped with a refractive index detector and two Varian Polymer Laboratories PolarGel-M columns in series (300mm x 7.5 mm). The lignins were dissolved and eluted with dimethylformamide with 0.1% lithium bromide using the following conditions: a flow of 0.7 mL/min and a temperature of 40 °C. The calibration of the HPSEC was carried using polystyrene standards of different molecular weights (between 62,500 and 266 g/mol) provided by Sigma Aldrich.

2.7.3.2. Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR analysis of the isolated lignins was carried out on a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two FT-IR spectrometer. A total of 8 scans were accumulated in transmission mode with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The spectrum was recorded from 4000 to 600 cm^{-1} .

2.7.3.3. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis of the different isolated lignins was carried out using a TGA Q5000 IR equipment (TA instruments). Between 5 and 10 mg of lignin were tested under a nitrogen atmosphere using a heating rate of 20 °C/min from 30 to 1000 °C.

2.7.3.4. Pyrolysis-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry analysis (Py-GC/MS)

The lignins isolated by the alkali delignifications were analyzed by Py-GC/MS using a 5150 Pyroprobe pyrolyzer (CDS Analytical Inc., Oxford, PA) connected to an Agilent 6890 gas chromatograph (GC) coupled to an Agilent 5973 mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies Inc., USA). The GC was equipped with a 30m x 0.25mm x 0.25 mm film thickness HP-5MS (5% phenyl)-methylpolysiloxane) column and helium was used as the carrier gas. The pyrolysis was performed at 600 °C (15s) reached at 20 °C/ms and with the interface kept at 260 °C. The GC oven was programmed to go from 50 °C (2 min) to 120 °C (5 min) at 10 °C/min, then to 280 °C (8 min) at 10 °C/min and finally to 300 °C (10 min) at 10°C/min. The compounds were identified by comparing their mass spectra with those from the National Institute of Standards Library (NIST), as well as, with compounds reported in the literature [19-21]. Peak molar areas were calculated for compounds with a peak area ratio higher than 0.4%, and the sum of the peak areas were normalized to 100% in order to determine the relative abundance of the identified compounds, as the peak area ratio could reflect the concentration of the different pyrolytic products [22].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of the autohydrolysis severity on the enzymatic digestibility of the vine shoots

In order to study the effect of the hydrothermal treatment on the enzymatic digestibility of the vine shoots for the production of glucose, the solids obtained in the hydrothermal treatments with severities (S_0) between 3.29 and 4.65 were subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis. The composition of the hydrothermally treated and enzymatically digested solids is collected in Table S1 (see Supplementary Material).

The susceptibility of the solid towards the enzymatic digestibility was estimated by the glucan to glucose conversion (GnGC,%). This parameter is defined as the ratio between the glucose generated in the enzymatic hydrolysis and the potential glucose contained in the autohydrolysed solids, which corresponds to the total conversion of glucan into glucose without degradation. The variation of the GnGC with the time for the different hydrothermally treated solids was fitted using the hyperbolic model proposed by Holtzapfle et al. [23], according to the following equation:

$$GnGC_t = GnGC_{max} \cdot \frac{t}{t + t_{1/2}} \quad (3)$$

where $GnGC_t$ (%) is the glucan to glucose conversion at time t , $GnGC_{max}$ (%) is the maximum glucose conversion at an infinite reaction time, and $t_{1/2}$ (h) is the time needed to achieve 50% of the $GnGC_{max}$. The parameter $GnGC_{max}$ measures the maximum possible enzymatic conversion under the assayed conditions and the parameter $t_{1/2}$ measures the kinetic of the hydrolysis.

Fig. 2a shows the glucose concentration profile during the enzymatic hydrolysis of the solids hydrothermally treated at different severities. In this figure, it can be appreciated that during the enzymatic hydrolysis of the solids pretreated at S_0 of 4.47 and 4.65 the sugar release occurs in two steps: a fast increase of the concentration of glucose in the media during the first 24 h followed by a slower and continued increase. This behaviour was also described by Requejo et al. [24] when they evaluated the enzymatic hydrolysis of hydrothermally treated barley straw. As expected, the increase of the severity of the pretreatment had a positive effect on the enzymatic digestibility of the hydrothermally treated vine shoots improving the glucose yield and decreasing the saccharification time.

In fact, the solid treated using the mildest conditions ($S_0 = 3.29$) presented the lowest glucose release, reaching a concentration of 3.44 g/L, whereas the solid obtained under the harshest autohydrolysis conditions ($S_0 = 4.65$) allowed the obtaining of a liquid phase with a glucose concentration of 14.32 g/L. Thus, this provoked an increase of the glucan to glucose conversion from 19.66% to 75%.

a

b

Figure 2. Glucose concentration profile in enzymatic hydrolysis of the autohydrolyzed solids obtained at different temperatures (a). Glucan conversion profile in enzymatic hydrolysis of the autohydrolyzed solids obtained at different temperatures (b).

The kinetics parameters ($GnGC_{max}$ and $t_{1/2}$) and the value of R^2 of the enzymatic hydrolysis are collected in Table S2 (see Supplementary Material). As it can be observed, the values of R^2 for all experiments were higher than 0.97, which indicates a good adjustment of the data to the proposed model. This is also reflected in Fig. 2b which displayed the representation of the experimental and calculated values of the $GnGC_{max}$.

It can be appreciated both in Fig. 2b and from the data of Table S2 (see Supplementary Material) that the highest values for the $GnGC_{max}$ were obtained with the solids pretreated at $S_0 = 4.47$ and 4.65 ($GnGC_{max} > 81\%$). With regard to the $t_{1/2}$, its value decreased for the solids obtained at the highest severities, going from 17.26 h at $S_0 = 3.29$ to 10.19 h at $S_0 = 4.65$. This trend is in agreement with the data reported by Requejo et al. [24] who carried out the enzymatic hydrolysis of autohydrolysed *Olea eriupea* trimmings.

The increase of the glucan conversion into glucose with the severity of the hydrothermal treatment could be related to the lower hemicellulosic content of the spent solids which decreased with the increase of the severity of the treatment, from 15.85% at $S_0 = 3.29$ to 2.54% at $S_0 = 4.65$ (see Table S1). In this aspect, Michelin and Texeira [25] described the hemicelluloses as a physical barrier for the enzymatic hydrolysis of the cellulose as they block the enzyme access to the cellulose surface. During the hydrothermal processing, the hemicelluloses are removed causing an increase of the available surface area of the cellulose, being this one of the possible explanations for the improvement of enzymatic hydrolysis after this processing [26].

Moreover, it is remarkable the low influence of the increase in lignin content on the enzymatic hydrolysis. As it can be seen in Table S1, although the lignin content on the solid increased with the severity of the treatment from 44.74% at $S_0 = 3.29$ to 55.09% at $S_0 = 4.65$, the enzymatic hydrolysis was improved. This could be explained by the disruption of the lignocellulosic structure caused by the hydrothermal treatment, such as the increase of the porosity of the biomass and the reduction of the crystallinity of the cellulose, which facilitates the enzymatic action [26]. Taking into account that the glucose yield was similar with the solids obtained at $S_0 = 4.47$ (74.01%) and $S_0 = 4.65$ (75.0%) for the following experiments the solid obtained at $S_0 = 4.47$ was employed since the difference in the glucose yield did not justify the energy necessary to work at higher temperature during the hydrothermal treatment.

In this study, apart from assessing the glucose generation for the bio-ethanol production, the hydrolysates obtained in the enzymatic hydrolysis were subjected to the determination of their total phenolic and acid soluble lignin (ASL) content, upgrading in this way the potential of the hydrolysates as value-added bio-products. As it can be seen in Table 1, the total phenolic content of the hydrolysates and the ASL solubilized during the enzymatic saccharification increased for the solids obtained under the harshest conditions. The increase of the severity of the hydrothermal

treatments causes a greater alteration of the structure of the lignocellulosic biomass leaving zones more exposed to the attack of the enzymes which from the obtained results seem to be able to solubilize small lignin fragments [27]. Therefore, the enzymatic hydrolysis allowed the simultaneous obtaining of phenolic compounds, acid soluble lignin and glucose. The recovery of these bioproducts from the enzymatic liquors could play an important role on the economic viability of the sustainable development of the bio-ethanol produced from vine shoots. In this line, Ofori-Boateng et al. [28] examined the potential of recovering both cellulose and phenolic compounds from oil palm fronds during the processes of a cellulosic ethanol biorefinery.

Table 1. Total phenolic content (TPC) and soluble lignin in acid (ASL) on the liquors at the end time of the enzymatic hydrolysis.

Severity (S_0)	ASL (%)	TPC (g/L)
3.29	1.24	0.18
3.45	1.40	0.21
3.60	1.44	0.23
3.82	1.46	0.26
4.01	1.61	0.31
4.28	1.90	0.32
4.47	1.96	0.33
4.65	1.94	0.34

3.2. Lignocellulosic ethanol production

In order to obtain a competitive concentration of bio-ethanol, it is necessary to work with high solids loading during the enzymatic saccharification. To accomplish this purpose, an additional experiment was performed using the solid pretreated at $S_0 = 4.47$ but working with a LSR 10 g/g (the loads of both enzymes were the same). In this case, the decrease of the LSR leads to an increase in the glucose concentration achieving 26.8 g/L, which is 1.9 times higher than the concentration obtained when a LSR of 20 g/g (14.32 g/L) was used. The decrease on the LSR involved a slight decline on the glucose yield (from 74.01% to 69.3%), which had been reported by other authors for similar experiments [24]. When the SSF treatment was carried out using the solid obtained during the hydrothermal processing at $S_0 = 4.47$ and using a LSR of 10 g/g, 13.3 g ethanol/L (corresponding to an ethanol conversion (EC) of 67.4%) were achieved after 48 h of SSF. The ethanol conversion is defined as the percentage of ethanol obtained with respect to the potential ethanol, which is calculated assuming the stoichiometric conversion of the glucan present in the solid to ethanol.

The results obtained are in agreement with the ones reported in similar studies. Requejo et al. [24] obtained an ethanol concentration of 23.2 g/L (EC = 72%) using autohydrolysed olive tree trimmings (operating at LSR = 8 g/g and an ESR = 10 FPU/g). Recently, Martínez-Patiño et al. [29] by performing an SSF of treated olive tree biomass with alkaline peroxide (90 min, 7% H_2O_2

and 80 °C), achieved 26.4 g ethanol/L, which corresponded to an EC = 68% (working at 10% solid loading and ESR = 15 FPU/g).

With the aim of accomplishing an integral valorization of the vine shoots, bio-ethanol was also produced using the liquid phase obtained in the autohydrolysis treatment at $S_0 = 4.47$ of the vine shoots. The liquors, which contained oligosaccharides, were posthydrolysed, neutralized and purified in order to obtain a dissolution rich in hemicellulosic sugars, being the xylose the most abundant one. In order to achieve a higher ethanol concentration, this dissolution was concentrated until 25 g xylose/L were obtained. After 72 h of fermentation, 9 g ethanol/L were obtained, which corresponded to an EC of 70%.

3.3. Recovery of the lignin from the residual solid of the SSF

Based on the composition of the residue obtained from the SSF assay (68.24% of lignin, 16.57% of glucan and 2.55% of hemicelluloses), this solid was subjected to a subsequent delignification treatment in order to recover the lignin as a secondary product from the ethanol production. The alkali delignification treatment permitted the removal of 65.23% of the lignin present in the SSF residue, being this data similar to the lignin solubilisation percentage reported by Dávila et al. [15] using autohydrolysed vine shoots as the substrate for an alkali delignification treatment. Analogous results were obtained by Lee et al. [11] and Guo et al. [30] during the alkali catalyzed organosolv and alkali delignification of the residue generated in the bio-ethanol production from oak wood and corn-stalks, respectively.

The chemical composition and the structural characteristics of the lignin isolated from the SSF residue were determined and compared with the ones determined for the lignins extracted by the same procedure from the untreated and the hydrothermally processed vine shoots at $S_0 = 4.47$. These comparisons were carried out to elucidate the possible modifications on the chemical composition, molecular weight distribution and thermal stability of the lignins which could be as a consequence of the cascading processing to which the vine shoots were subjected until the obtaining of bio-ethanol. Moreover, this analysis can be useful to determine the stage of the biorefinery scheme in which is more suitable to carry out the lignin extraction in function of the application to which it will be intended [27].

3.3.1. Analysis of the purity of the isolated lignins

The lignin isolated from the SSF residue (SSFL) presented a high purity, being composed by 87.54% of Klason lignin, 2.55% of glucose, 3.05% of xylose, 1.21% of ASL and 0.26% of ashes. The lignin extracted from the autohydrolysed vine shoots (AHL) also presented a high Klason lignin content (70.24%), while the lignin obtained from the untreated vine shoots (VSL) showed a lowest purity (48.76%), as it can be seen in Table 2. The high purity of the SSFL and AHL could be attributed to the effective removal of the hemicellulosic and cellulosic fractions during

the autohydrolysis and the SSF assays of the vine shoots, respectively. In fact, the lignin extracted from the untreated vine shoots presented the highest hemicellulosic sugars content (31.03% of xylose). Interestingly, the ASL content of the extracted lignins decreased with the successive stages of the processing of the vine shoots (Table 2).

Wang and Chen [31] studied the influence of the pretreatment on the composition of the black liquor and consequently on the purity of the precipitated lignin. These authors carried out a steam explosion of corn stalks with a $S_0 = 3.65$ prior to an alkali delignification and they compared the results with the composition of the black liquor obtained from untreated corn stalks. They observed that the pretreatment produced an increase of the Klason lignin content from 50% to 92.96% while the carbohydrate content decreased from 45.83% to 4.56%. Lee et al. [11] also obtained a lignin with a high purity (84.46%) from the residue generated in the bioethanol production using popping treated oak wood.

Regarding to the percentage of lignin extracted from the three studied substrates, it was remarkable that it was similar for the autohydrolysed solid and the residual solid obtained in the SSF (67.67 and 65.38%, respectively). However, in the case of the untreated vine shoots, a 59.6% of the lignin present in the vine shoots was extracted. This behaviour could be explained by the structural alterations that the raw material suffers during the autohydrolysis and SSF treatments, which could ease the subsequent delignification process.

Table 4. Composition of the alkali lignins isolated from the untreated vine shoots (VSL), from the spent solid obtained after the autohydrolysis treatment (AHL) and from the residue obtained after the (SSFL).

	VSL	AHL	SSFL
Klason lignin (%)	48.76	70.24	87.54
ASL (%)	3.08	2.38	1.21
Glucose (%)	2.46	2.16	2.55
Xylose (%)	31.03	3.27	3.05
Ash (%)	ND	ND	0.26

ND: Not determined

3.3.2. Structural and chemical characterization of the isolated lignins

The chemical and structural characteristics of the lignins could determine the suitability of the lignin for a given application. Qiao et al. [32] suggested that the lignin extracted from the ethanol residue obtained by a SSF treatment, exhibits better chemical reactivity than either lignosulfonate or Kraft lignins for their employment in the production of polyurethanes, epoxy resins, or copolymers. Jin et al. [33] synthesized phenol-formaldehyde adhesives modified with the lignin extracted from the residue obtained after the ethanol production.

3.3.2.1. FTIR analysis.

The three extracted lignins were analyzed by Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy in order to determine their main functional groups. The three recorded FTIR spectra presented the typical bands observed in lignins extracted from other raw materials by different procedures [30,34]. However, as the lignins were isolated after different treatments of the raw material, variations in the intensity of some bands were observed. Tana et al. [27] also observed differences in the intensities of some bands of lignin samples isolated from the main stages of the typical cellulosic ethanol production process from sugar cane bagasse.

As it can be seen in Fig. 3, the main difference between the three analyzed lignins, was the intensity of the band observed at 1030 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the stretching and bending vibration of C-O, C-C and C-OH and glycosidic C-O-C, which indicates the presence of hemicelluloses (Sun et al., 2012). The intensity of this band was lower for the AHL and SSFL than for the VSL, being this attributed to the removal of the hemicellulosic fraction during the autohydrolysis treatment. This band could also be associated to the in-plane bending of guaiacyl rings, which could explain the presence of this band in the AHL and SSFL although they presented low carbohydrate content according to the purity results shown in section 3.3.1. The low carbohydrate content of the SSFL and AHL could also be corroborated by the reduction of the intensity of the band observed at 912 cm^{-1} which corresponds to the presence of β -glycosidic linkages between xylopyranoses [35].

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra of the lignins obtained after each step of the biorefinery scheme.

The FTIR spectra of the three lignin samples showed a wide band at 3372 cm^{-1} which corresponded to the stretching vibration of the hydroxyl groups, being this band more intense for the SSFL than for the VSL and AHL. The bands observed at 2935 cm^{-1} and 2849 cm^{-1} are related

to the C-H stretching vibration in methyl and methylene groups, while the band at 1457 cm^{-1} is ascribed to the C-H bending vibration of the same groups, being them more noticeable in the spectra of the SSFL than in the ones of the VSL and AHL. The aromatic structure of the lignin in the three samples was reflected in the bands located at 1595 cm^{-1} , 1512 cm^{-1} and at 1422 cm^{-1} . The presence of the guaiacyl and syringyl units was confirmed by the bands observed in the FTIR spectra of the three lignins, although they presented the highest intensity for the SSFL. The bands observed at 1324 cm^{-1} , 1113 cm^{-1} and 813 cm^{-1} corresponded to the syringyl ring breathing with C-O stretching and to the C-H inplane and out of plane deformations of the syringyl ring respectively. The presence of the guaiacyl rings was proved by the bands observed at 1214 cm^{-1} and at 912 cm^{-1} which belonged to the guaiacyl ring breathing [36] and to the out of plane bending. However, this last band could also associated to the presence of hemicelluloses as it was mentioned above.

3.3.2.2. HPSEC analysis of the isolated lignins

The three isolated lignins were also analyzed by HPSEC to determine their molecular weight distribution. Their average molecular weight (Mw), number average (Mn) and polydispersity index (Mw/Mn) are collected in Table 3.

The different processes to which the vine shoots have been subjected influenced strongly the molecular weight distribution of the extracted lignins. The 14.25% of the lignin extracted from the untreated vine shoots presented a Mw of 154,927 Da, a lignin fraction with such a high Mw was not observed in the lignins isolated from pretreated vine shoots (AHL and SSFL). The high Mw of the VSL could be attributed to the presence of polysaccharides in the lignin, as during the alkaline delignification the solubilisation of polysaccharides could take place, remaining them covalently link to the lignin [34]. According to the results observed during the purity analysis carried out to the three isolated lignins in section 3.3.1, the VSL was the lignin with the higher carbohydrate content (mainly hemicelluloses). Without taking into consideration the high molecular weight fraction of the VSL, it seemed that the SSFL presented the highest molecular weight. 60.74% of the SSFL presented a Mw of 55,987 Da while the main fraction of the AHL (49.28%) presented a Mw of 29,807 Da and the main fraction of the VSL (29.58%) presented a Mw of 9009 Da. Both the autohydrolysis and the enzymatic hydrolysis which takes place in the SSF, could facilitate the cleavage of inter-bonds or ether bonds present in the lignin [37,38], favouring condensation reactions, which could explain the higher Mw of the SSFL. The higher polydispersity index observed for the SSFL (27.52) compared with the ones observed for the AHL and VSL (13.39 and 19.51, respectively) could confirm that condensation reactions have taken place during the bio-ethanol production from hydrothermally processed vine shoots [39].

Table 3. Weight average (Mw), number average (Mn) and polydispersity index (Mw/Mn) of the alkali lignins isolated the untreated vine shoots (VSL), from the spent solid obtained after the autohydrolysis treatment (AHL) and from the residue obtained after the (SSF), taking into account the different fractions.

	VSL						AHL						SSFL					
%	14.25	29.58	29.40	19.86	6.91	Whole	49.28	19.80	13.68	15.14	2.10	Whole	60.74	25.22	7.51	5.39	1.15	Whole
Mw	154927	9009	1420	692	364	25327	29807	1759	818	355	192	15212	55987	1195	362	236	280	34348
Mn	120509	5108	1339	667	356	1298	8360	1649	788	362	191	1136	10035	981	353	35235	277	1248
Mw/Mn	1.28	1.76	1.06	1.038	1.02	19.51	3.56	1.07	1.04	1.06	1.01	13.39	5.57	1.22	1.02	1.00	1.009	27.52

3.3.2.3. Total phenolic content (TPC)

An important feature to consider in the structure of the lignins is the presence of phenolic hydroxyl groups since they are related to the antioxidant activity and to the suitability of this aromatic biopolymer to synthesize adhesives [6]. This characteristic was evaluated through the determination of the total phenolic content (TPC) by the Folin-Ciocalteu assay, which takes into account all the hydroxyl aromatic compounds [40]. The lignins isolated from SSF residue and from the hydrothermally processed vine shoots presented a TPC of 42.57 and 44.57 g GAE/100 g, respectively, while the lignin extracted from untreated vine shoots showed the lowest TPC content (26.21 g GAE/100 g of lignin). In view of these results, we can affirm that the subsequent treatments of the vine shoots increased the TPC of the isolated lignins, being the TPC values for the AHL and SSFL close to each other. The TPC values of the SSFL and AHL were significantly higher than what it has been reported in the literature for alkali lignins. García et al. [41] obtained an alkali lignin isolated from *Miscantus sinensis* with a TPC of 14.19 g GAE/100 g lignin and they observed an increase of the TPC when the lignin was obtained from the autohydrolysed *Miscantus sinensis* (22.73 g GAE/100 g lignin). The higher TPC value of the SSFL and AHL could be associated with the removal of the hemicellulosic and cellulosic fractions during the processes of the vine shoots, as García et al. [42] suggested but it could also be related to the influence of these treatments on the lignin structure.

3.3.2.4. Pyrolysis-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS)

In order to obtain more information about the phenolic composition of the extracted lignins, they were subjected to a pyrolysis coupled to a gas chromatograph and a mass spectrometer. The identification of the compounds present in the pyrolytic products of the three lignins is displayed in Table 4. The lignin derived compounds have been classified in four groups according to their aromatic structure: guaiacol type (G), phenol type (P), syringol type (S) and catechol type (C) [43]. As reflected in Table 4, the profiles of the phenolic compounds determined by the pyrolysis of the three studied lignins were roughly similar. However, due to the different processing of the vine shoots, the relative abundance of these pyrolytic compounds varied between the three lignins. From the identified phenolic compounds, syringol, 3-methoxy catechol, 4-vinyl syringone, 4-methyl guaiacol, phenol, guaiacol and p-cresol were the dominant products. In general, the peak molar area of each phenolic compound increased with the processing of the vine shoots, as it can be seen in Table 4. The content of catechol and syringol type compounds increased with the successive processing of the vine shoots; however, this behaviour was not followed by the content of guaiacol type compounds as it is slightly higher for the AHL than for the SSFL. The presence of the catechol type compounds between the determined phenolic compounds could be attributed to the degradation of the syringyl units due to the high temperature employed during the pyrolysis, as Ma et al. [44] suggested. The presence of the phenol type compounds could be due to

demethoxylation reactions from the aromatic ring of guaiacyl or syringyl units or to the cracking of CeC inter unit linkages among the p-hydroxyphenyl units of the lignin or from Ref. [45]. Apart from phenolic compounds carbohydrate derived compounds such as furfural or furfuryl alcohol were also identified between the pyrolytic products of the different lignins. These compounds could be generated during the pyrolysis of residual carbohydrates [34]. As it is displayed in Table 4, during the pyrolysis of the VSL the highest carbohydrate derived compounds were produced while the lowest amount were determined for the SSFL, which is in agreement with the results obtained during the analysis of the purity of the different lignins.

Table 4. Distribution of the main compounds obtained in the pyrolysis of the isolated lignins.

Compound	Rt (min)	m/z	Origin	%VSL	%AHL	%SSLF
Toluene	4.03	91, 92, 65	-	-	0.69	0.63
Furfural	4.97	96, 95, 67	Carbohydrate	8.13	0.65	0.34
Furfuryl alcohol	5.21	98, 97, 81	Carbohydrate	0.60	-	-
Phenol	7.45	94, 66, 65	H	3.30	4.57	4.7
<i>o</i> -cresol	8.65	108, 107, 77	H	0.69	1.04	1.02
<i>p</i> -cresol	8.98	107, 108, 77	H	3.25	3.68	3.98
Guaiacol	9.28	109, 124, 81	G	3.01	4.03	4.47
2,4-dimethyl phenol	10.29	107, 122, 121	H	-	-	0.85
4-ethyl phenol	10.47	107, 122, 77	H	0.67	-	-
2-ethyl phenol	10.67	107, 122, 77	H	-	0.74	-
4-methyl guaiacol	11.33	138, 123, 95	G	-	7.85	5.48
Catechol	11.43	110, 64, 53	C	1.93	-	3.47
3-methyl catechol	13.07	124, 78, 123	C	-	1.17	-
3-methoxy catechol	13.25	140, 125, 97	C	2.32	4.23	6.93
4-ethyl guaiacol	13.77	137, 152, 122	G	3.34	2.27	2.45
4-methyl catechol	14.16	124, 123, 78	C	-	2.27	2.26
3,4-dimethoxy phenol	15.99	154, 139, 111, 151	S	0.86	-	2.8
Syringol	16.01	154, 139, 111, 96	S	2.39	6.63	7.72
Vanillin	17.15	151, 152, 81	G	-	0.82	0.97
Acetovanillone	18.90	151, 166, 123	G	-	1.47	1.26
4-vynil syringone	20.20	180, 165, 137	S	2.36	5.36	6.09
4-allyl syringol	20.75	194, 91, 119	S	-	0.69	0.82
Syringaldehyde	21.58	182, 181, 111	S	0.7	1.21	0.9
Acetosyringone	22.53	181, 196, 153	S	0.68	1.52	1.24
Total syringyl derivates			S	6.99	15.41	19.57
Total guaiacyl derivates			G	6.35	16.44	14.63
Total p-coumaryl derivates			H	7.91	10.03	10.55
Total catechol derivates			C	4.25	7.67	12.65

3.3.2.5. Thermogravimetric analysis.

The thermal stability of the lignins is an important structural feature for their employment in biomaterials or biocomposites and it could be influenced by the composition of the lignins. The thermal degradation of the three different isolated lignins was analyzed by carrying out a thermogravimetric analysis. The information about the maximum weight loss temperature (T_{max}) and the quantity of the char residue that remains after each thermogravimetric analysis is collected in Table 5 and the corresponding thermogravimetric curves (TGA) and the first derivate curves (DTG) are shown in Fig. 4a and b, respectively. As it can be seen in Fig. 4a, all the lignins present

an initial weight loss below 110 °C in which the samples lost around a 6.5% of their mass. This initial weight loss is associated to the evaporation of the water present in the samples.

Table 5. The maximum weight loss temperature and the char residue that remained after the thermogravimetric analysis of the different lignins.

	T_{max}^a (°C)	Solid residue (%)
VSL	277.98	35.58
AHL	400.00	49.12
SSFL	39	42.28

Fig. 4. Thermogravimetric analysis spectra (a) and derivative DTG curves (b) of alkaline lignins extracted from the untreated vine shoots, from the autohydrolyzed vine shoots and from the SSF residue.

Except from this initial degradation step, which is common for the three lignins, the VSL presented a thermal degradation behaviour completely different from the ones observed for the

AHL and for the SSFL. The VSL showed two main degradation processes at $T_{\max} = 277\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T = 371.95\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The thermal stability of the AHL and SSFL was higher as it can be seen in Fig. 4a. They started to degrade at higher temperatures and less drastically than the VSL. The AHL and SSFL presented two decomposition processes at $T = 318.28\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{\max} = 400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T = 333.56\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{\max} = 396\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. The lower thermal stability of the VSL was associated to its higher carbohydrate content. According to Watkims et al. [46] the second degradation step observed in the AHL and SSFL could be caused by the degradation of the carbohydrate present in the lignins, as it takes place between 180 and 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, while the third degradation step could be associated to the degradation of the lignin, which occurs above 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. However, due to the low carbohydrate content of the SSFL and AHL, the second degradation step observed in these lignins could be also attributed to the decomposition of weak chemical bonds in $\beta\text{-O-4}$ linkages present in the lignin structure [47].

As it can be seen in Table 5, the char residue that remains after the thermogravimetric analysis was also influenced by the composition of the isolated lignin. The VSL presented the lowest char residue (35.58) due to its highest decomposition rate, which is associated to its high carbohydrate content. According to Guo et al. [47] the percentage of char residue is related to the condense structure of the lignin.

3.4. Mass balance of the integrated processing of pretreated vine shoots

Fig. 5 shows the flow chart of the vine shoots processed by an autohydrolysis at $S_0 = 4.47$ followed by a SSF treatment and a subsequent alkali delignification to produce bio-ethanol and lignin from the vine shoots. Considering the overall mass balance of the process, per 100 kg of autohydrolysed vine shoots, 13.3 kg of bioethanol were produced by the SSF, which is in the range of data reported by other authors [48]. Moreover, at the end of the SSF, an exhausted solid was recovered containing a high amount of lignin (68.24%) and a low content of glucan and hemicelluloses (16.57% and 2.55%, respectively). Taking into account the composition of this residual solid, the lignin was recovered as the obtaining of a lignin side-stream with potential value could be considered a suitable option to improve the economic viability of the lignocellulosic ethanol production [49]. From the overall balance of the revalorization process, per 100 kg of autohydrolysed vine shoots 35.55 kg of Klason lignin were recovered by alkali treatment. After the delignification treatment of the LER, the cellulose that remained in the delignified LER (7.12 kg/100 kg autohydrolysed vine shoots) could be attributed to the crystalline cellulose which was not hydrolysed by the enzymes during the SSF stage. The high lignin content of the autohydrolysed vine shoots (45.38 kg/100 kg autohydrolysed vine shoots) could also prevent the complete enzymatic hydrolysis of the cellulose as it increases the material recalcitrance [50].

Fig. 5. Overall balance of the integrated processing of pretreated vine shoots.

4. Conclusions

In summary, the increase of the severity of the hydrothermal processing led to an improvement of the susceptibility of the autohydrolysed solids towards an enzymatic hydrolysis, achieving a glucose yield of 74.01% for the solid obtained at $S_0 = 4.47$. This solid was subjected to a SSF experiment to obtain bio-ethanol reaching an ethanol conversion of 67.4% after 48 h. The extraction of lignin following each stage: untreated vine shoots, autohydrolysed vine shoots and bio-ethanol residue produced a lignin with higher purity and higher thermal stability however, the lignin obtained after SSF showed a higher molecular weight than the other lignins. The lignin isolated from the residue obtained after the SSF treatment presented the highest contents of total syringol and catechol derivatives whereas the lignin extracted from autohydrolysed vine shoots presented the highest content of total guaiacyl derivatives. The lignin extracted from the untreated vine shoots presented the lowest amounts of lignin derived compounds. The three isolated lignins were subjected to the same extraction treatment, so the differences observed in their structure are attributed to the changes provoked by the different stages of the bio-ethanol production. Therefore, a good knowledge of the structure of these lignins is essential to define its valorization strategy to improve the economic viability of the bio-ethanol production from vine shoots.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.04.131>.

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